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Title: SOP to turn On and Off the Orbitrap Fusion and the Vanquish Duo UHPLC system.

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Make a note about the LC-MS turn On/Off and baking the Orbitrap Chamber to Logbook.

SW: Xcalibur 4.7.69.37, Thermo Scientific SII for Xcalibur 1.8.0.530, Orbitrap Fusion Tune 4.2.4321

To turn Off Orbitrap Fusion and Vanquish Duo UHPLC system

1. In Orbitrap Fusion Tune Application (Tune window), place the MS to Off Mode (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Power mode icons showing the selected mode

2. Close all the programs on the screen.
3. For the MS, place the Electronics service switch to Service Mode (down), wait 10 seconds and then place the Main Power switch to Off Mode (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. The power entry module is located on the right side of Orbitrap Fusion

4. By using the on/off valve close the supply line for Nitrogen ECD 5.5.
5. Turn Off Vanquish Duo by the system power button (the front left side of the Vanquish system base). Turning Off each LC module by its main power switch.
6. Turn Off both the syringe holder on the back of the device and the divert valve by socket unplugging.
7. Turn Off the PC.

To turn On Orbitrap Fusion and Vanquish Duo UHPLC system

1. By using the on/off valve open the supply line for Nitrogen ECD 5.5 and wait 5 mins. Check the output pressure of **3.5 bar for Nitrogen ECD 5.5** remains unaffected.
2. For the MS, place the Main Power switch to On Mode while the Electronics service switch is still to Service Mode (down) and wait at least about 1 hour to allow the MS to pump down (Figure 2).
This turns on the fans, the forepump and the turbomolecular pumps. LEDs on the front panel are off.
If the MS was turned Off for extended time, pump down the vacuum system for at least 15 hours.
3. For the MS, place the Electronics service switch to Operating Mode (up) to initialize sequence restart.
Power LED on the front panel turns green. The Vacuum, Communication and System LEDs remain Off.
4. Turn On the PC, sign in by the Recetox account and wait until the PC connects to local network.
Indication appears on the right side of the bottom screen banner.
5. If not, click *Orbitrap Fusion Console* icon to open the Fusion Console software. After a few minutes, the PC to MS connection initializes and “FT booting” notification appears.
By completing the MS startup process, the Vacuum and Communication LEDs are green, and the System LED is yellow.
6. Turn On the Vanquish Duo LC by the system power button. Additionally, turn On each LC module by its main power switch.
7. Turn On both the syringe holder on back of the device (panel displays initial parameters) and the divert valve (it displays 1 or 2 indicating to the MS or waste position).
8. By clicking the *Orbitrap Fusion Tune* and the *blue X* icon, open the Tune window (the MS is loaded to Standby Mode) and Xcalibur, there go to Instrument Setup. At Thermo Xcalibur Instrument Setup window, open the SII Xcalibur and check Direct Control to monitor the LC.
9. Bake out the Orbitrap Chamber:
 - a) In the Tune window, place the MS to Off Mode (Figure 1).
 - b) By the *wrench* icon open the Diagnostics, to the search box fill-in Vacuum and choose System\Vacuum\Bake Orbitrap Chamber. Set parameters 12 for Bake Time (hours) and 2 for Cooling Time (hours) and click Start.
10. Following the Orbitrap Chamber baking:
 - a) Store the generated diagnostic PDF report, e.g.: YYYY-MM-DD_DiagPos_Bake_Orbitrap_Chamber to appropriate file in Calibration Reports shortcut.
Check the acceptability for **UHV Pressure gauge** (Orbitrap) that passed value **below 5×10^{-8} Torr**.
 - b) Check the **threshold limits <3.0 Torr and $<1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ Torr** for **Source Pressure gauge** and **Ion Gauge Pressure gauge**, respectively.
 - c) In Tune window, place the MS to Standby mode (the temperature of ion transfer tube increases) and then let the MS stabilize overnight.
11. Calibrate the MS in positive mode first.

Note: The used figures were obtained from Orbitrap Tribrid Series (Thermo Fisher Scientific): Getting Stared Guide and Hardware Manual

ANNEX**When it starts, the Orbitrap Fusion Console 4.2.4321 displays notifications like:**

FT booting

Instrument booting

FT connected

Instrument connected

Peripherals – syringe pump, divert valve, turbo pump 1, turbo pump 2, UHV pump

USB Turbo 1 speed: 800

USB Turbo 2 speed: 1200

USB Turbo 3 speed: 999

OT pressure is high: 7,093 e -07

Software version: 4.2.4321

Entering main Loop:

When it starts, the panel on the syringe holder displays:

Status:	id Max: 40.00	Min: 0.30
Syringe:	3.26 id (mm)	Find Syringe
Volume:	500 µL	
Rate:	3 µL/min	
Delay:	0 min	Select units